

Table 2. Weight of honeydew of some WBPH populations, Bogor, Indonesia.

Colony	Honeydew ^a (mg/female)			
	TN1	Citanduy	B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	Colombo
Muara Lawai	7.21 a A	1.09 a B	0.55 a B	1.15 a B
Bulu Kumba	858 a A	0.81 a B	0.49 a B	0.53 a B
Munggu	4.85 a A	1.18 a A	0.52 a A	2.39 a A
Mataram	5.05 a A	2.44 a A	1.12 a A	1.57 a A
Greenhouse	8.74 a A	0.96 a B	0.56 a B	1.67 a B

^a Identical small letters in a column or capital letters in a row indicate no significant difference at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 3. Population increase of WBPH from different colonies on 1-mo-old rice varieties, Bogor, Indonesia.

Colony	Population increase ^a				
	TN1	Citanduy	B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	IR36	Colombo
Muara Lawai	1217 a C	497 b AB	919 a BC	334 a A	99 ab A
Bulu Kumba	623 a A	174 a A	289 a A	538 a A	144 ab A
Munggu	760 a A	127 a A	355 a A	1084 a A	212 b A
Mataram	904 a C	138 a AB	834 a C	496 a BC	75 a A
Greenhouse	964 a C	352 ab B	788 a B	549 a B	24 a A

^a Identical small letters in a column or capital letters in a row indicate no significant difference at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 4. Survival of WBPH nymphs on 1-mo-old rice varieties at 10 d after infestation, Bogor, Indonesia.

Colony	Survival ^a (%)				
	TN1	Citanduy	B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	IR36	Colombo
Muara Lawai	78 a C	22 a A	67 a BC	32 a AB	5a A
Bulu Kumba	65 a BC	30 a B	40 a BC	70 a C	2a A
Munggu	52 a BC	13 a AB	47 a BC	67 a C	0a A
Mataram	80 a D	13 a AB	43 a BC	70 a C	0a A
Greenhouse	87 a D	55 a AB	60 a BC	75 a C	3a A

^a Identical small letters in a column or capital letters in a row indicate no significant difference at the 5% level by DMRT.

recorded responses to these populations and one greenhouse population at BORIF of rice varieties Citanduy, B4032d-Mr-1-3-1, IR36, TN1 (susceptible check), and Colombo (resistant check) in seedbox screening tests with three replications (Table 1).

Reaction parameters were honeydew excretion (10 replications), population buildup (3 replications), and survival and development (3 replications). Rices were in a split-plot design with varieties as main plots and insect populations as subplots.

Reaction of rice varieties to different WBPH colonies was uniform. TN1 was susceptible to all colonies, but Citanduy, B4032d-Mr-1-3-1, Colombo, and IR36 were moderately resistant (Table 2). Population increase of colonies differed only slightly on the varieties tested (Table 3). Survival of nymphs also was similar on resistant varieties (Table 4). *J*

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Association of traits governing cold tolerance at early seedling stage in rice

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Degree of yellowing of seedlings and mortality count are measures of cold

tolerance in many countries. In the US, seedling height is the criterion for evaluating cold water tolerance 4 wk after sowing. In Taiwan, cold tolerance is based on the percentage of winter survival. At IRRI, I measured cold hardiness by computing a tolerance

index (TI) based on degree of discoloration and percent survival of the seedlings compared to a resistant check.

I screened 23 parents and their 102 hybrids (17 lines × 6 testers) for cold tolerance at the early seedling stage to evaluate the cultures for relative cold

Correlation coefficients^a between tolerance index (TI) and other attributes of rice at early seedling stage. IRRI, 1986.

Character	Seedling height on			Discoloration score on			Survival (%) on		TI based on survival on	
	Day 8	Day 15	Day 22	Day 8	Day 15	Day 22	Day 15	Day 22	Day 15	Day 22
Emergence coefficient	0.661**	0.310**	0.194	-0.315**	-0.141	-0.093	0.115	-0.031	0.141	0.084
Seedling height, day 8		0.555**	0.541**	-0.471**	-0.375**	-0.292**	0.257**	0.023	0.322**	0.225**
Seedling height, day 15			0.869**	-0.877**	-0.857**	-0.807**	0.808**	0.520**	0.836**	0.749**
Seedling height, day 22				-0.819**	-0.789**	-0.789**	0.732**	0.567**	0.770**	0.743**
Discoloration score, day 8					0.892**	0.869**	-0.834**	-0.564**	-0.869**	-0.793**
Discoloration score, day 15						0.938**	-0.889**	-0.634**	-0.931**	-0.814**
Discoloration score, day 22							-0.932**	-0.716**	-0.956**	-0.883**
Survival (%) day 15								0.707**	0.981**	0.899**
Survival (%) day 22									0.695**	0.798**
TI based on survival, day 15										0.907**

^a * = significant at P <0.05, ** = significant at P <0.01 levels.

tolerance and to determine interrelationships, if any, between traits used as evaluation criteria.

Twelve presprouted seeds, 1 row per culture, were sown in soil-filled porcelain trays with adequate nutrient and water, and then kept in artificially lighted Koiotron KG cabinets at 15 ± 0.5 °C for 3 wk. Each tray contained 10 test cultures and the resistant check Fujisaka 5 distributed at random. There were two replications.

Emergence data were recorded every 4 h for 12 d. The seedlings were scored

as emerged when the shoot tip was visible on the soil surface. An emergence coefficient was worked out based on speed and vigor of emergence. The cultures were scored for discoloration (1 = plants have natural color, 9 = almost dead or dead plants) at 8, 15, and 22 d. Seedling height of the seedlings in a culture was also measured. Survival percentage of the emerged seedlings was recorded at 15 and 22 d on a scale of 0-1. The sum of survival scores for each culture per replication was converted to a percentage of the

average score of Fujisaka 5.

TI, emergence coefficient, seedling height, and discoloration scores were the criteria used for evaluating genotypes for cold tolerance at the early seedling stage.

Intercharacter associations between TI and other traits are shown in the table. TI or cold tolerance at early seedling stage is positively correlated with seedling height at 15 and 22 d, negatively correlated with leaf discoloration score at 8, 15, and 22 d, and positively correlated with percent survival at 15 and 22 d. *ℒ*

Evaluation of rice genotypes for cold tolerance at vegetative stage

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Ninety F₁ hybrids and their 21 parents were transplanted in 2.25-m single-row plots, with 3 replications, in the cold tolerance screening nursery at the CES, RDA, Chuncheon. Plants were subjected to cold water stress at 17 and 20 °C in separate blocks from 20 d after transplanting until maturity at a constant water depth of 5 cm. Cold tolerance at the vegetative stage was measured by leaf discoloration, scored twice at 17 °C and once at 20 °C. The average of the three observations were used for statistical analyses.

None of the six IRRI lines used as pollinators had a leaf discoloration score of 3 or lower (Table 1). Among the

Table 1. Mean and general combining ability (GCA) effects of parents for leaf discoloration score in Chuncheon, Korea, 1986.

Parent	Mean	GCA effects
Males (IRRI lines)		
IR29506-60-3-3-2	5.4	-0.455**
IR8455-K2	5.4	-0.213**
IR9202-10-2-1-5-1	5.8	0.047
IR8866-30-14	5.9	0.496**
IR7167-33-2-3	6.3	-0.147*
IR15889-32-1	6.4	-0.022
		SE (gi) ± 0.069
Females (indica)		
Leng Kwang	3.4	0.716**
Shoa-Nan-Tsan	4.2	1.610**
Suweon 281	4.5	0.566**
Silewah	5.2	0.627**
Samgangbyeon	5.5	0.655**
K39-96-3-1-1-1-2	5.6	1.960**
China 988	6.3	1.938**
Females (japonica)		
Stejaree	1.3	-1.023**
SR3044-78-3	1.3	-0.845**
SR5204-914-1	1.5	-1.051**
Shimokita	1.7	-1.379**
K84	1.7	-1.084**
Barkat	1.8	-0.995**
K332	2.0	-0.990**
Suweon 235	2.0	-0.706**
	LSD 5% = 0.74	SE (gi) ± 0.109
	LSD 1% = 0.98	